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A Creative Folio

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Fancy Gaze

My eyes were captivated.
What a wonderful visage.

The eyes,
The eyelashes,
The nose,
The lips,
The teeth,
The skin tones,
The curvature.

Esoteric!

That emptiness of my impulse
Everything turns into ashes,
And the fruit of my desire was in dismay.